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Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced

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Catalogue of TAIS

- Deliverable D5.4 -

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D5.4. Catalogue of TAIS [May, 2022]

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About RAISD	
Call (part) identifier	H2020-SC6-MIGRATION-2018
Topic	MIGRATION-08-2018 Addressing the challenge of forced displacement
Fixed EC Keywords	Globalisation, migration, interethnic relations
<p><i>Forced displacement crises overcome societies and institutions all over the world. Pushed by the urgencies rather than events, solutions are frequently reactive, partial, and disregard some groups. The project 'Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced' (RAISD) aims at identifying highly Vulnerable Groups (VG) among these forcibly displaced people, analysing their specific needs, and finding suitable practices to address them. The concept of 'vulnerability context' considers the interplay between the features of these persons and their hosting communities, their interactions and experiences, and how different solutions for attention and inclusion affect them. As a result of this work, a methodology to carry out these studies will be developed. These goals are aligned with the call. They pursue characterizing these migrations and developing suitable aid strategies for them. The Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) frames the project. It proposes that all actors (including civil society) co-design actions, transversely integrates the gender perspective, and supports sustainability. Our research strategy will be based on methodological triangulation (i.e. the combined application of several methodologies). We will implement it through a specific participatory action research approach to fulfil the aim of undertaking advocacy-focused research, grounded in human rights and socio-ecological models. The team will work as a network of units in countries along migration routes. The units will promote the VG people' involvement, so they can speak with their own voices, gather information, and test practices. Work will rely on a tight integration of Social and Computer Sciences research. Automated learning and data mining will help to provide evidence-based recommendations, reducing a priori biases. A software tool will support collaboration, continuing previous H2020- funded RRI work.</i></p>	

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Executive Summary

This paper presents the [Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies](#) (TAIS) implemented in the RAISD ([Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced](#)) project (2019-2022). The objective of the catalogue is to describe the eight TAIS designed and implemented in seven project countries - Finland, Hungary, Italy, Jordan, Lebanon, Spain and Turkey – and to analyse their aims and outcomes. The report provides a practical approach to RAISD TAIS, and it may be useful for those planning and implementing tailored services for people in forced displacement situations.

This document is the final deliverable of Work Package 5 (WP5 – Design of tailored attention and inclusion strategies) and it both draws on and contributes to other RAISD artefacts. More detailed information about the planning and implementation of the TAIS can be found in other project deliverables, particularly deliverable 5.3 (Tailored attention and inclusion strategies: Definition and Guidelines). This paper is based on the information provided by project partners about their TAIS activities implemented during the three project cycles, described in TAIS final reports by each consortium member team.

1 What is a TAIS?

The tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies (TAIS) refer to innovative, tailored and personalized services designed to respond to the specific needs of people in vulnerable situations. These contextualised strategies aim to constitute effective ways of dealing with the needs of forcibly displaced people (FDP) in vulnerability contexts (VC). The TAIS presented in this paper are based on RAISD (Reshaping Attention and Inclusion Strategies for Distinctively vulnerable people among the forcibly displaced) project (2019-2022).

Forcibly displaced people refer to persons “who are forced to move, within or across borders, due to armed conflict, persecution, terrorism, human rights violations and abuses, violence, the adverse effects of climate change, natural disasters, development projects or a combination of these factors” (United Nations 2018, 3). However, while armed conflicts and human rights violations are deeply interrelated to social and economic drivers of migration, distinguishing forced and voluntary migration is not straightforward (Crawley and Skleparis 2018). In the TAIS presented in this paper, the forcibly displaced people include people with different legal statuses: asylum seekers, migrants with rejected asylum applications, and people with refugee status or those entitled for international protection.

In RAISD, each TAIS have been designed to fit their specific *vulnerability contexts*. Different vulnerabilities are relevant in each context and different strategies need to be implemented in each context. Therefore, in RAISD, ‘vulnerability’ refers not only to individual people or features of certain groups but also to qualities of communities and societies. Consequently, we do not assume the existence of predetermined, static ‘vulnerable groups’ but highlight the centrality of contexts and situations for understanding vulnerability and acknowledging the structural conditions that produce vulnerabilities for some people. During the project, drawing from the empirical work conducted in the partner countries, we have identified four vulnerability contexts: context of survival in the Middle East, context of fragmented aid in Southern Europe, context of hostility in eastern Europe and context of control in Nordic countries (for a more detailed account, see deliverable 4.3 ‘Catalogue of vulnerability context’).

In the South, mainly in the Middle East, vulnerabilities are often acute. Millions of FDP live in poverty and suffer from deficient living conditions. In these contexts, individuals, families and communities must find ways to survive with the support of various non-governmental agents, because they are poorly recognised by state authorities. In Southern and Western Europe, the number of FDP is smaller than in the Middle East, but the population is heterogeneous. Public authorities responsible for asylum policies in these countries often lack resources and are incapable of fully recognising the manifold needs and vulnerabilities of FDP. One can thus find several small and medium-size NGOs promoting the well-being of FDP with diverse interests and agendas. The defining feature of both Eastern and Northern European contexts is the state control of FDP populations. Another common denominator between the two contexts is the small number and relative homogeneity of the FDP population. Only few have the resources to enter the farthest corners of Europe via irregular routes. In Eastern Europe, states tend to be hostile toward FDP and aim to expel them without concern for their rights or wellbeing. In Northern Europe, although there is a lack of explicit state-level hostility, the FDP population is heavily controlled.

The work of eight piloted TAIS presented in this paper was carried out by RAISD consortium partners in seven countries: University of Helsinki (UH), Finland; Hungarian Association for Migrants (Menedék), Hungary; European

Centre for Studies and Initiatives (CESIE), Italy; Yarmouk University (YU), Jordan; Lebanese International University (LIU), Lebanon; Complutense University of Madrid (UCM), Spain; and Anadolu University (AU), Turkey. Moreover, in each country, a variety of stakeholders (organizations, specialists, civil society representatives, activists, migrants etc.) took part in developing and implementing the TAIS. The starting point for the TAIS design was the field research including 25 interviews of FDP in each country in 2019. After that, the TAIS were designed, implemented and evaluated in three cycles in 2020-2021. Due to COVID-19 pandemic, initial re-design of the TAIS were necessary in Spring 2020, and the pandemic and consequential restrictive measures challenged their implementation.

The ethical and methodological foundations included Socio-Ecological Model, Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI), Action Research Strategy, SMART Criteria and Actor-Oriented Evaluation. Central to these methodologies was the flexibility and adaptation to contextual and changing needs of the participants, as well as the inclusion of beneficiaries and stakeholders in the planning and implementation of the TAIS. Ethical issues such as gender equality, informed consent and respect for diversity were respected throughout the project. (For a more detailed account on methodology, see deliverable 3.4 'TAIS methodology and guidelines').

Each TAIS was tailored to fit the local environment and to respond to context-specific vulnerabilities. Partly stemming from the sensitivity to contexts, TAIS targeted different beneficiaries. In this paper, TAIS are presented in two clusters. The first cluster includes TAIS which aimed to directly support forcibly displaced people by providing or facilitating services or education for them. The second cluster includes TAIS which aimed to support forcibly displaced people indirectly by promoting the competencies of people working with FDP. These two clusters are analytical classifications constructed after the TAIS implementation and although the TAIS are set in one of the clusters, some of them include elements of the other cluster as well. (For detailed description of each TAIS, see deliverable 5.3 'Tailored attention and inclusion strategies: Definition and Guidelines'.)

The report consists of three main parts. First, each TAIS is introduced comprehensively. Second, the aims and outcomes of the TAIS are examined. Third, TAIS are analysed in relation to their forms, contents and perspectives. Finally, the findings are summed up in the conclusion chapter.

2 Descriptions of the TAIS

2.1 Cluster 1: Supporting forcibly displaced people

Five of the eight TAIS aimed to directly support forcibly displaced people by providing them certain services or education in the particular vulnerability context. The services developed and provided in the TAIS were an online discussion forum (Finland I), child-care activities (Finland II), a learning tool (Italy), psychological support forum and trainings (Jordan), and an entrepreneurship and employment program (Spain). Below, these TAIS are introduced one by one.

2.1.1 Multilingual online forum – Finland I

A voluntary group of young asylum-seeking men were invited to join, together with Finnish-speaking voluntary young men, in an online thread to discuss the experiences of asylum seekers and everyday life in Finnish society. The aim was to promote the learning of both asylum seekers and volunteers. The former group learned the language and Finnish culture from the perspective of ordinary men and received information about various possibilities in Finland. As for the latter group, Finnish men were able to have first-hand knowledge about the lives of asylum seekers in Finland and about their home countries. Further, both groups developed their skills in online communications. The online discussions were moderated and, when necessary, translated from languages used by asylum seekers into Finnish. Moreover, two asylum-seeking peer moderators were recruited during the second and third piloting rounds to instigate discussions and, when necessary, to help in translating the messages. Each forum lasted approximately five weeks.

2.1.2 Development of child-care services in reception centres – Finland II

The TAIS aimed to develop child-care services in reception centres in Finland. To promote the wellbeing of asylum-seeking families with small children, child-care activities were developed together with the Finnish Red Cross (FRC) reception centres. The general state of child-care services in FRC reception centres was surveyed and two reception centres providing comparatively wide-ranging child-care services were involved to further develop their activities. Child-care activities of the two centres were observed and parents and professionals involved were interviewed. The knowledge acquired was used to qualitatively improve the content of the child-care activities. Moreover, a trial of more regular child-care services was carried out in one reception centre. As a result, a model for child-care services for reception centres was established, to be used for all reception centres throughout Finland. In addition, the knowledge collected in the TAIS was used to argue the importance of asylum-seeking children's access to municipal early childhood education and care services.

2.1.3 ALL you can LEARN - a selective learning tool – Italy

The ultimate aim of the TAIS was to increase learners' decision-making capacity as they are to be intended as "co-experts", thus having the opportunity to decide and co-design their learning experience according to a set of individual variables (interests and aspirations, level of studies and previously attended programmes, language knowledge, logistics and time availability, etc.). Expected results of the Italian TAIS included the increased highly

vulnerable and forcibly displaced female participation in education and training; decreased initial resistance and attendance reluctance; reduced in-training dropout rates among FDP women. In order to achieve these goals, the excessive strictness of learning paths and hours of commitment were avoided and replaced by a flexible learning environment. The actual piloting of "ALL you can LEARN" involved forcibly displaced women living and/or exposed to highly vulnerable situations and conditions, victims of human trafficking currently living in Sicily, originally from Ivory Coast, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Somalia, Comoros and Tunisia.

<https://cesie.org/en/higher-education-and-research/allyoucanlearn-training-experience/>

2.1.4 Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF) – Jordan

In Jordan, a Psychosocial Refugee Support Forum (PRSF) was developed to spread awareness about asylum seekers' psychological and social support, reflecting the social responsibility for supporting the needs of asylum seekers in terms of mental health and psychological aid. The main goal of this program was to enable asylum seekers to be self-reliant, independent, and with little or no need for external support. Early identification of psychological distress and trauma, and effective care were essential in discovering the strengths that asylum seekers could rely on to face their daily challenges and benefit from existing opportunities. PRSF was designed to deliver various services that contribute to minimizing the effects of psychological and social challenges. These services included psychological services, social support, family services, healthcare access, economic support, and legislative support. They would contribute to improving the asylum seekers' lifestyle and enable them to integrate into the host community. Moreover, trainings about financial, legal and health awareness for refugees were provided in the Jordanian TAIS.

2.1.5 Refuge of power: Sub-Saharan women's entrepreneurship and coaching program – Spain

The TAIS aimed to develop competencies to promote the socioeconomic inclusion of sub-Saharan refugee women or applicants for international protection in Spain, as well as to foster the beneficiaries' self-reliance, autonomy and general level of work market competence. The program focused on different skills and capacities (digital, emotional, communication, leadership, management and entrepreneurship) that had been selected to form part of the program, then validated by researchers, stakeholders, professionals, and some potential beneficiaries in the consultation processes. These skills also stood out for having a high value for the job market, and the professional and personal development of the beneficiaries. The Spanish TAIS translated into a very flexible social intervention process, highly adaptable to the needs and demands of the participants and the COVID-19 context. The participating women were highly engaged and formed an active group in the design, development, and evaluation of the practices. The TAIS was a training and support process with a twofold course of action: In terms of entrepreneurship and strengthening of abilities and competencies.

2.2 Cluster 2: Promoting capabilities of people working with forcibly displaced people

The rest three of the eight TAIS aimed to support the forcibly displaced people mainly indirectly by promoting the competencies of people working with FDP. These people were social and health care professionals (social workers, psychologists, health care workers), legal advisers and volunteers providing services for FDP in civil society organisations (Hungary), students (Lebanon), and municipal social service workers and administration

representatives (Turkey). The TAIS promoted professionals' and other actors' competencies through education and training activities. Below, these TAIS are introduced one by one.

2.2.1 *Trajectory monitoring toolbox for social workers working with refugees – Hungary*

In Hungary, the objective of the TAIS was to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures. Social workers and service providers analysed individual cases in order to build a “Trajectory monitoring toolbox” of helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. The toolbox was built around evidence-based “vulnerability profiles” and the description of the trajectories that these typical cases should follow in the institutional field, to prevent the accumulation of vulnerabilities and reduce the isolation of vulnerable individuals. Social workers and service providers in Hungary should be informed about who, where, and how to apply helpful and tailored interventions for vulnerable refugees. The toolbox had the primary objective to recognise and assess a context of vulnerability. Based on its content, institutions and organisations can improve their internal workflow, as well as for inter-institutional cooperation, to make trajectories less demanding and vulnerability reduction more effective. The toolbox contains two major elements: a Handbook and a Self-reflection tool.

2.2.2 *Health 4 SEAD “Health, Social-Emotional, Academic, Development”- Lebanon*

In Lebanon, the designed TAIS addressed the social, emotional, and academic problems. The programme aimed to impact the Syrian people living in camps. It delivered a holistic coronavirus awareness to children, pregnant women, the elderly, malnourished people, and people who are ill or immune-compromised. The TAIS aimed to deliver an online awareness campaign called Health 4 SEAD “Health, Social-Emotional, Academic, Development”. The outcome of this pilot project aimed at empowering a strong pool of NGOs and Information Focal Point networks all over Lebanon in preparing them to facilitate and support their teaching efforts of displaced people in refugee camps. This was done through the LIU Health Committee's active participation and sharing of practical experiences utilising online means. Essentially, the programme centred around a plethora of different skills and capacities that were chosen to be a constituent of the programme.

2.2.3 *Accessing and Participating in Basic Daily life Practices through Monitoring – Turkey*

The TAIS implemented in Turkey aimed to develop the service providers' capacity to monitor service quality on the specific needs and challenges (especially regarding the challenges experienced while accessing the daily life practices) of forcibly displaced women and girls. The AU team conducted an assessment of service providers working with vulnerable groups on behalf of the government – mainly employees of municipal social service and local administration representatives. Service providers should know the need- and rights-based approaches and advocacy issues when working with vulnerable groups. Inclusion, diversity, and monitoring training were provided for service providers' capacity development. The trainings aimed to provide basic information and measure the knowledge, skills, and attitudes of service providers. Pre-test and post-test methods were used to measure the impact of each training.

3 Aims and outcomes of the TAIS

This chapter discusses the aims and outcomes of the eight RAISD TAIS in three subsections through four criteria: *capabilities* referring to the level of autonomy of FDP and their ability to cope in new surroundings; *inclusion* referring to FDP's access to institutions and communities of the host society; and *capacities* and *competencies*, former referring to everyday skills and knowledge learned by FDP and latter referring to professional skills and knowledge learned by the people working with the vulnerable FDP. These analytical categories are derived from the evaluation framework of RAISD project (see deliverable 7.4 'Evaluation Criteria: Actor-oriented and integrated evaluation'). The objective is not to provide a detailed report of all elements of each TAIS, but to present generally and with illustrative examples of how capabilities, inclusion, and capacities and capabilities were promoted in the piloted TAIS. When evaluating the outcomes of the TAIS, it needs to be kept in mind that the TAIS were implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic and consequential restrictive measures as lockdowns influenced both the implementation and the outcomes of the Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies for FDP in each vulnerable context.

3.1 Increasing capabilities: Coping and autonomy

Capability refers to actual possibilities people have when trying to achieve the goals they aspire. This includes both the available resources and the circumstances in which these resources can be used. Thus, capability is not only about individual assets, but also about abilities to use and benefit from them in certain contexts. In the TAIS of both clusters, the extensive aim was to increase the capabilities of vulnerable FDP. The capabilities of FDP were promoted by increasing their coping skills and autonomy in the context of the host society. Autonomy refers to the ability of individuals to pursue the goals that are the most desirable for them.

Increasing coping and autonomy of FDP were at the core of many TAIS in **cluster 1**. In Jordan, the psycho-social support forum aimed to improve psychological wellbeing by providing access to care services providing psychological and social support and improving individuals' psychological coping strategies. The provision of child-care activities in Finland aimed to increase wellbeing of children by providing them meaningful activities with supportive adults to mitigate the harms caused by the forced displacement and increase coping of their parents by providing them a moment of child-care to ease their everyday life in a stressful situation.

The autonomy of FDP was promoted in the TAIS by facilitating or providing access to certain services. For example, the autonomy of asylum-seeking parents in Finland was promoted by providing them child-care to have time to take care of their own wellbeing, run errands or participate in study activities. On the other hand, in some TAIS, the ideal form of autonomy was independence of services and they aimed to enable the FDP "to be self-reliant, independent, and with little or no need for external support" (Jordan) or to encourage the FDP "avoiding behaviours of dependence on the workers of the entities or third parties" (Spain). The autonomy of FDP was promoted in different spheres and levels. In Spanish TAIS, autonomy was related to stable socioeconomic position, income and work which were fostered by promoting work market competencies of program participants. In Italian TAIS, the autonomy was pursued by proving an opportunity for participants to use an online learning tool to decide and co-design their learning experience according to a set of individual variables.

In **cluster 2**, improving wellbeing of FDP was a central objective of the Lebanese TAIS that aimed to maintain the health of people in refugee camps by spreading COVID-19 awareness. The Hungarian TAIS aimed to ease the coping of FDP by developing a tool for NGO service providers to enhance the identification of vulnerabilities, so they could find right and effective ways to alleviate them and to provide more fluid service trajectories for FDP searching for assistance. The TAIS of Turkey did not have a direct linkage to coping or autonomy of FDP, but it aimed to improve municipal services for FDP by awareness rising through diversity and monitoring trainings for municipal employees. The TAIS in cluster 2 also paid attention to the wellbeing and coping of the people working with the FDP. For instance, the Hungarian TAIS aimed to ease the emotional burden of the social workers who provide the services to migrants, and trainings in Lebanon had a positive impact on the coping of the students-refugees who were trained to educate people in the camps.

In the TAIS, capabilities are strongly related and intersect with inclusion and capacities that are discussed in the following chapters. On the one hand, the promotion of coping and autonomy of FDP is supporting inclusion in the host society and its institutions. On the other hand, the improvement of skills and knowledge of FDP and professional competences of service providers, as well as supporting FDP's contacts and access to institutions, services and communities are tools to increase coping and autonomy of FDP.

3.2 Promoting inclusion: Access to institutions and communities

Inclusion denotes a broad idea of the position of FDP in relation to host communities and society: social connectedness, labour market participation, educational degrees, community engagement and access to services. Subjective inclusion relates to feelings of belonging to local communities and host society, while objective inclusion refers, for instance, to ties with majority representatives, service use and access to educational institutions and the labour market. In the eight Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies, FDP's inclusion to host societies was promoted by facilitating their access to societal institutions and structures, such as labour market, education or certain services, or promoting contacts with local people, in the particular vulnerability context. Moreover, many of the capabilities discussed above, as well as the skills and knowledge discussed below, were tools used by TAIS pilots to support FDP's inclusion to host societies.

In some of the TAIS in **cluster 1**, the aim was to promote FDP's inclusion in society by promoting participation in a particular societal sphere. For instance, in the Spanish TAIS, the aim was to promote participants' access to the labour market either through self-employment or as employed workers. In other two TAIS, the field of participation was education: the Italian TAIS provided an online learning tool as a response to FDP women's education and training drop-outs, and in Finland, child-care activities were provided to asylum-seeking families who have no access to regular early childhood education, to provide education for children and to ease parents' participation in study activities. The psychosocial support forum by the Jordanian TAIS aimed to promote asylum seekers' inclusion in psychological and social services by supporting their access to different services via an online platform by connecting FDP searching for support with service providers ready to assist them.

In some TAIS, inclusion was promoted and cohesion created in more informal settings, instead of institutional involvement: the multilingual discussion group (Finland I) promoted ties between voluntary asylum-seeking men and Finnish-speaking voluntary young men, aiming to increase trust between these two groups. Moreover, some TAIS

promoted peer-support and intragroup cohesion among the pilot participants: In the Spanish and Italian TAIS, fellow programme participants and in the Finnish II TAIS, other child club members provided a group to belong to and to share experiences with, while the access to communities or services of host society was denied or difficult.

TAIS in **cluster 2** promoted FDP's inclusion by focusing on service providers, and upgrading their practices when providing services for FDP. In the Hungarian TAIS, the aim of monitoring social workers' work was to enhance refugees' embeddedness in social structures by easing to define where, how and by who to apply helpful interventions for refugees, and by documenting "the silent knowledge" of experienced professionals. Moreover, the TAIS improved the cooperation between different NGOs providing services to FDP: it increased the trust and clarified the division of labour between them, thus, simplifying the inclusion and access of FDP in need of assistance. In the TAIS of Turkey, the trainings for local government representatives and municipal social workers were not aimed to promote the FDP's access to services, but their inclusion was aimed to be enhanced by revising and turning employees' attitudes more favourable toward refugees. In the Lebanese TAIS, the inclusion of FDP in the camps was not in the focus, but the student-refugees participating in the trainings developed supportive relationships inside and outside the university.

3.3 Improving capacities and competences: Skills and knowledge

Capacity refers to people's abilities to steer their everyday lives. Concretely in the TAIS, improved capacities were the skills and knowledge of FDP. *Competence* refers to the service providers' abilities to provide services. In the TAIS, competencies of people working with vulnerable FDP were improved by enhancing their professional skills and knowledge. The aim of improving the capacities of FDP and the competences of service providers was to increase capabilities (coping and autonomy) of FDP and to promote their inclusion in the host society.

In many TAIS in **cluster 1**, improvement of capacities through learning different skills and knowledge was central. The skills improved in the TAIS were both "hard" skills including leadership and management (Spain), digital/online skills (several TAIS) and language (several TAIS) as well as "soft" skills such as emotional skills (Spain, Finland II, Jordan) and self-awareness and decision-making capacity (Italy). In some TAIS, the improved skills had a clear focus: the entrepreneurship and coaching program (Spain) was primarily focusing on entrepreneurship and work-related skills and the multilingual online forum (Finland I) on communication skills. In other TAIS, the improved skills were more extensive in the first place: for instance, the child-care activities (Finland II) aimed to improve a variety of fundamental skills (socio-emotional, motoric, cognitive) of children.

One of the recurrent skills focused on in the TAIS were language skills. Learning the Finnish language was one of the main aims of the multilingual discussion group and child-care services (Finland I and II). Moreover, in some TAIS language learning was not the main aim, but was included to support other aims of the TAIS. For instance, a Spanish conversation course was provided for the participants before the actual programme (Spain) and participants of the Italian TAIS reported improvement in their Italian skills. Another set of skills included in quite many TAIS were digital/online skills. In the multilingual discussion group, one aim was to develop both asylum-seeking and Finnish voluntary men's online communication skills (Finland I), improving digital and communication skills was an inherent part of the entrepreneurship and employment supporting programme (Spain), and digitalization was one of the

themes of the online learning tool (Italy). The need for improving these skills increased due to the COVID-19 pandemic and the consequential online implementation of many TAIS services and activities.

In addition to skills, providing knowledge was crucial in many TAIS in cluster 1. This was maybe most evident in the online learning tool (Italy), which included education on a wide range of themes (active citizenship and democracy; health and wellbeing; life skills; social cohesion, equity and equality; employment and work; digitalisation; and inclusive societies and cultures). Also other TAIS included information about legal, institutional and cultural structures and services of the host country. Awareness of FDP's human rights as fundamental rights (Spain, Jordan) and women's rights (Spain) was provided in some TAIS. The multilingual discussion group provided asylum seekers information about Finnish culture from the perspective of volunteer Finnish men and information about various possibilities in Finland. In the Spanish TAIS, knowledge about the economy and labour market in Spain was laid as a foundation for learning activities aiming to foster the employability of the programme participants. In the Jordanian TAIS, the idea of the online support forum was to provide information about asylum seekers' psychological and social support as well as spread information about financial, legal and health awareness through trainings.

However, the TAIS in cluster 1 did not only provide knowledge to FDP, but also raised awareness of actors of the host society. For instance, in the multilingual discussion group, voluntary Finnish men were able to have first-hand knowledge about the lives of asylum seekers in Finland and their countries of origin (Finland I). Moreover, professionals providing services for FDP learned themselves about different cultures (Spain, Finland II) and global and national migration frameworks (Spain). In addition, an important outcome of many of the TAIS was fostering networking and information sharing among different stakeholders in the field of forced migration, as well as transformations of services based on knowledge produced in the TAIS.

In TAIS in **cluster 2**, the education was primarily targeted to professionals and different stakeholders working with the FDP to improve their professional competencies. The learning of skills and knowledge were promoted in order to provide better services for vulnerable FDP. Knowledge was at the core of these TAIS. In Lebanon, the TAIS was an online awareness-raising campaign related to COVID-19 and healthcare. In the TAIS, health and COVID-19 awareness of FDP was spread online and through training students, who were refugees themselves, and supposedly working with other people in refugee camps in Lebanon. In the TAIS of Hungary and Turkey, the knowledge provided was related to forced migration and vulnerabilities, as well as to the service provider's own position and influence when working with FDP. Service providers were provided information about inclusion, diversity and FDP's living conditions (Turkey) and contextual vulnerabilities (Hungary) to tackle misinformation, misunderstanding and problematic attitudes of the helpers. In addition, they were introduced to new ways of encountering the FDP and reflecting and improving their own work to make vulnerability reduction of FDP more effective. In Hungary, the education was modified in the form of a handbook and a self-reflection tool for professionals, particularly social workers in NGOs, while in Turkey, the education was conducted by a series of trainings to enhance the capacities and awareness of municipal social workers and local government employees.

A key element of Hungarian TAIS activities was to improve professionals' self-reflection skills. Other skills of people working with FDP improved in the TAIS in cluster 2 were digital/online skills that were fostered in the TAIS of Lebanon by providing the students video instructions on how to use basic online and computer software.

4 Approaches of the TAIS

In this chapter, different approaches of TAIS are discussed in three subsections. *Forms* of the TAIS refer to the modes of the pilots and their implementation: who is the TAIS targeted at; is it about implementing a new service or improving or transmitting existing services; are the TAIS activities reproducible; and are the TAIS activities implemented face-to-face or in online environments. *Contents* include the topics and focus of the TAIS, as variety and scale of the themes as well as the inclusion of supporting activities in addition to the main pilot contents. *Perspectives* refer to TAIS approaches to the involvement of beneficiaries, the direction of the learning process and, finally, the targets of improvements and education.

4.1 Forms of the TAIS

The shared aim of the eight pilots was to improve vulnerable FDP's inclusion by Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies, while they by design took divergent forms originated from differing vulnerability contexts, as well as composition of and reflection by each consortium team. Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant effect when project partners were choosing appropriate layouts for their TAIS.

The TAIS activities were implemented with the service providers and service users in the contexts of NGOs, universities and municipalities. One element related to a form of the TAIS is already included in the two clusters where the TAIS are placed in this paper: Even though all the TAIS aimed to alleviate vulnerabilities of the FDP, some of them were directed straight to FDP (Finland I&II, Italy, Jordan, Spain), while others were directed to people working with them (Hungary, Lebanon, Turkey). In the initial stage of the TAIS design, the beneficiaries were defined based on FDP and stakeholder interviews by the research and implementation team in each national context. However, the success in reaching the intended beneficiaries – either the vulnerable FDP or the service providers - in actualised TAIS activities varied between the TAIS. In some TAIS, a new service was designed and piloted (Finland I, Italy, Jordan, Spain), while other TAIS were about developing existing services (Hungary, Finland II). Promoting FDP's access to other existing services was part of some TAIS (Jordan, Hungary). In a few TAIS (Lebanon, Turkey), the pilot activities were merely training lessons.

The scale of the beneficiaries of the TAIS differed. In some TAIS, the pilot was implemented with a small, closed group of participants whose capabilities, inclusion and capacities were improved (Finland I&II, Italy, Spain). In these groups, beneficiaries were provided individual and personal support in addition to general educational and other activities and the group itself had a supportive function. The peer-support and recognition by these groups was evaluated as one of the main successes by the participants, regardless of theme of TAIS. In other TAIS, the activities were more generic or targeted to wider audiences. While all TAIS implemented piloting activities during the project time, many of them produced documented materials enabling to repeat the piloted activities or other ways to utilize the TAIS experiences after the project. For instance, models for child-care and multilingual discussion group (Finland I&II), online learning tool (Italy), online support forum (Jordan) and toolbox (handbook and self-reflection tool) for social workers (Hungary) are resources that can be used to alleviate vulnerabilities of FDP after the RAISD project.

One element that became crucial in the piloted TAIS, partly due to social distancing policies caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, was the location of the organised activities either in present or in online environment. In some TAIS, as

the multilingual online discussion group in Finland, the piloted activities were in advance designed as online-based. Some other TAIS had pre-planned online elements, such as the web-based learning materials in Italian TAIS, which were, however, intended to be taught in person. In the rest of the TAIS, the activities were planned to be implemented inherently as face-to-face activities. Despite the pandemic, some of the activities were succeeded to carry out in person, as child-care services in Finland, albeit after a delay. However, most of the TAIS needed to adapt to the changing environment by applying online methods, at least to some extent, or by modifying the face-to-face activities. Implementing online measures had both negative and positive consequences, most of which were related to the accessibility of the TAIS activities. Based on experiences on RAISD TAIS, online methods require various resources by participants, such as sufficient language and technological skills as well as suitable material equipment. Moreover, recruitment for online-programs may be difficult without face-to-face contacts. The activities with professionals and stakeholders were, probably due to better resources, less harmed by the transition to online communication or even benefitted from no need to be physically present in a certain location. Undoubtedly, accessibility issues are important in face-to-face activities as well.

4.2 Contents of the TAIS

As the forms of the TAIS, also the contents of them were related to the identified vulnerabilities in the particular context. The variety of eight TAIS included a range of different fields and topics: social and health care (Jordan, Lebanon, Hungary, Turkey), education (Italy, Finland II), labour market (Spain) and mundane communication (Finland I). The previous chapter on the aims and outcomes (chapter 3) of the TAIS introduces what kind of contents the TAIS included in relation to the capabilities, inclusion, capacities and competencies of FDP and the people working with them.

In addition to variety in the main themes and topics between the different TAIS, they were different in relation to themes and topics inside a specific TAIS. Some of the eight TAIS had a quite narrow focus, while others included different thematic areas more widely. For example, the learning tool in Italy included a variety of thematic areas (active citizenship and democracy; health and wellbeing; life skills; social cohesion, equity and equality; employment and work; digitalisation; and inclusive societies and cultures) as well as the trainings in Jordan (psychological services, social support, family services, health care access, economic support, and legislative support). The Spanish TAIS focused mainly on learning contents related to the labour market, but moreover, the program included other themes such as knowledge about rights and language learning and, thus, had a quite holistic perspective on promoting the capabilities of the participants. On the other end of the spectrum was, for example, the Lebanese TAIS focusing merely on COVID-19-awareness, in addition to basic online skills.

Another element related to contents was to what extent the TAIS were concentrating on their main activities and to what extent they included supporting activities. While other TAIS were providing merely materials (Lebanon, Hungary, Turkey) or a certain service (Jordan), others were enabling or supporting beneficiaries' participation by providing different resources. However, it is clear, that additional assistance is needed to support the participation of vulnerable FDP, while professionals or employees, supposedly, have better resources to attend on behalf of and supported by their organisations. The supporting activities were often related to the accessibility of the TAIS activities. For example, in some TAIS, tablets and laptops with internet connections were borrowed for programme participants in face-to-face trainings (Italy) or in order to enable their online participation during the meeting

restrictions related to the pandemic (Spain). In many TAIS (Lebanon, Italy), additional support was needed in relation to the online modality. In the Italian TAIS, attendees who were mainly women with children, were provided child-care, some TAIS arranged or supported transportation to the premises the activities took place (Finland II, Spain) and some TAIS provided support related to language, such as translation in online discussions (Finland I) or a language course (Spain). Moreover, some TAIS also included emotional support, as a social worker (Spain), personalized support in addition to group activities (Finland I, Spain) and group engagement activities such as dance-movement therapy (Italy).

4.3 Perspectives of the TAIS

A central idea of the TAIS methodology was to include the participants in the development and implementation process of the pilot. The implemented TAIS enabled a different level of participation in the design of the pilot. In the Spain TAIS, for instance, the participants were actively involved in the process and had a significant impact on how the TAIS was realized. In Hungary, the social workers using the handbook and self-reflection tool were incorporated in creating the materials. In Italy, the group- participants were able to choose learning contents they found suitable for them, but the online tool and contents themselves were pre-designed. In most TAIS, a few potential beneficiaries had an influence on the design process of learning materials (Jordan, Lebanon, Italy) or content of the services (Finland I&II), but the activities were mainly pre-designed for participants to step in and take part. In Turkish TAIS, the trainings were designed and implemented by the experts. In all TAIS, participants were able to comment on the activities during or after them in order to evaluate and improve the TAIS further.

In addition to the inclusion of participants in the development and implementation process of the TAIS, there were differences in the direction of the learning process the pilots facilitated. Some TAIS utilized bidirectional methods and supported mutual learning. For instance, the starting point of the multilingual discussion group (Finland I) was to support the learning of both asylum-seeking men and Finnish speaking men and to position members of both groups as learners and educators. In some TAIS (Jordan, Lebanon, Turkey), the learning was merely organised as traditional top-down teaching in which the experts gave lessons to the audience. In some of these TAIS, the participants called for more interactive stance.

In most of the TAIS targeted to the FDP (cluster 1), the main measure to tackle the vulnerabilities of FDP was to empower them by increasing their awareness about their own rights and the structures of the host society, and by improving their personal skills to promote their inclusion, coping and autonomy. Thus, these TAIS provided FDP resources and competence to increase their personal resilience to adapt and cope in the given vulnerability context. In these TAIS, on the one hand, FDP were positioned as capable actors competent to have an effect on their own life and future. On the other hand, improving FDP's situation can also be perceived as the host society's task, not only a responsibility of individuals in vulnerable situations. In the TAIS, there were also attempts to influence the institutional level of the host society to ease the situation of the FDP. In some TAIS in cluster 2, professionals and other people working with FDP were educated about the vulnerabilities, experiences and needs of the FDP and provided competencies not to deepen but alleviate their vulnerabilities. Thus, they were impacting at the institutional level. Also some TAIS primarily targeted FDP (cluster 1) had some effects to the individuals and institutions of the host society. Here the challenge is, if the developed tools and their aimed positive effects reach the individuals and alleviate their vulnerabilities in obtained manner.

5 Conclusion

This paper has presented the Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies developed and implemented in the RAISD-project. Through the descriptions, classifications and analysis of the eight TAIS in seven project countries, this paper has discussed elements related to piloted activities and services that aimed to alleviate vulnerabilities of the forcibly displaced people in different contexts on the route from the Middle East to Northern Europe.

The report shows, how capabilities, inclusion and capacities of vulnerable FDP can be improved by increasing their autonomy and coping, by promoting their access to institutions and services of the host society, by improving their skills and knowledge in various ways, and by enhancing competences of people working with them. In RAISD TAIS, coping in current situation and increase of autonomy (capabilities) were increased by providing tailored services and by supporting participants' independency. Inclusion was promoted by supporting FDP's paths to institutions and informal networks of the host society. Manifold skills were improved and expedient knowledge was provided for both FDP (capacities) and people working with them (competences) to promote FDP's capabilities and inclusion. Hence, these elements – capabilities, inclusion, capacities and competences - are interrelated.

Moreover, the paper presents different approaches related to forms, contents and perspectives that can be applied when providing Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies to FDP in vulnerable contexts. Most of the RAISD TAIS aimed to improve the situation of the vulnerable FDP by providing them tailored services while the rest were targeted to people working with the vulnerable FDP. Based on the analysis, both approaches have positive features, such as empowering peer-support in closed group-based activities of FDP and increased co-operation of different stakeholders in the field of forced migration. Regarding the forms of the pilots, the turn towards online measures, largely resulted by COVID-19 pandemic, showed up both possibilities and challenges of such measures. As for the contents, TAIS included both focused and thematically more extensive pilots. Some of the TAIS were not just content on providing their main activities but took into account the possible insufficiency of participants' resources of and ensured the accessibility and acceptability of activities by holistic approach and by providing supportive services. Finally, the TAIS differed in relation to participants' inclusion in the development and implementation process of the TAIS as well as to the direction of the learning process. Here, the comprehensive incorporation of the targeted FDP appears desirable, as well as participatory and mutual learning instead of one-way top-down teaching.

Based on RAISD experiences, successful Tailored Attention and Inclusion Strategies may contain various topics and forms. What is important, is to make certain that, first, the aims of the activities are based on needs of the targeted FDP, second, the means are consistent with the aims and the particular vulnerable context, and third, the TAIS is able to adapt to internal and external challenges and changes. A focal method to respond on these points is the profound inclusion of FDP in the design, implementation and reshaping the activities and services, a shift from "helping" vulnerable FDP to "acting together" to tackle the difficulties constructed by vulnerable contexts.

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RAISD D4.3 Catalogue of vulnerability context (University of Helsinki)

RAISD D5.3 Tailored attention and inclusion strategies: Definition and Guidelines (Menéndez)

RAISD 7.4 Evaluation Criteria: Actor-oriented and integrated evaluation (University of Helsinki)

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D5.4. Catalogue of TAIS [May, 2022]

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